

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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ABOUT THE OAEBU DATA TRUST EFFORT

Originating in 2015, the OAeBU Data Trust effort has brought over 100 individuals across five continents together to surface and address the issues that complicate the analysis and use of book usage metrics for decision making and open access advocacy. To date, the project has documented the complex OAeBU data supply chain,² launched pilots of open-source infrastructure for a usage data trust, and facilitated workshops to understand the ways in which scholars and specific staff roles at libraries, publishers, and publishing platforms and services rely on OAeBU data. While these use cases were documented to inform data trust service development, the project team recognizes that they provide broader insights into the evolving analytics and linked data demands across the scholarly communications ecosystem.

METHODOLOGY

This document evolved from the outputs of multiple virtual ideation sessions and workshops among peer stakeholder groups. These community-oriented feedback mechanisms were advertised via the OAeBU Data Trust effort's communities of practice. Co-Editors Drummond and Hawkins translated meeting and asynchronous ideation outputs into a preliminary use case document, which was shared back for public comment via the project's communities of practice and social media.³ Public comment was incorporated into this document, with notes offered by community members included at the end of each section. Within this document, staff roles at university presses that work with usage data are identified as personas. Then, use cases are listed with descriptions of why usage data is important or how it is applied for a given use case. Specific questions or queries of usage data that surfaced in discussion are noted.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Book publishers, publishing platforms and services, and libraries all rely on book usage data to inform their operations. Across these industries, staff must address the burden of managing and curating usage data provisioned in COUNTER-compliant and non-compliant reports,

1 https://educopia.org/data_trust/and <https://zenodo.org/communities/oaebu>

2 Clarke, Michael, & Ricci, Laura. (2021, April 9). OA Books Supply Chain Mapping Report. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4681725>

3 The OAeBU project's processes for communities of practice development and use case development are published in Drummond, Christina (2020). "Engaging Stakeholder Networks to Support Global OA Monograph Usage Analytics," Collaborative Librarianship: Vol. 12 : Iss. 2 , Article 9. <https://digitalcommons.du.edu/collaborativelibrarianship/vol12/iss2/9>

APIs, dashboards, and spreadsheets. These institutions individually manage, compile, and link usage data metrics, some of which are provisioned via dashboard services for users ranging from scholars, research offices and funding agencies, to editors, collections and acquisitions managers, and administrative decision makers.

While the term “usage data” is often used today to refer to web analytics reports that tally page visits and file downloads, the use cases herein document a near future where linked usage data analytics regularly inform book publishing and scholarly communications operations. Publishers and libraries expressed interest in using OAeBU data analytics to inform overall investment, strategy and fundraising in OA programs. They noted how data on the location and context of access to OA eBooks can inform book marketing and dissemination strategy, acquisitions and collections development, and scholars’ promotion and tenure. OAeBU data also surfaced as vital to supporting the promotion of OA publication among scholars and to illustrating institutional impact on the local and global stage. Linked contextual usage data can illustrate how OA books reach targeted audiences in classrooms, among scholars, within industry, and among policy-makers.

OAeBU data is poised to inform customer service relationships as publishers and libraries seek to appreciate service provider niches, evaluate book hosting and dissemination arrangements, and understand what is returned from their OA investments. Simultaneously, publishing platforms and services leverage usage data to inform the research, development, sales, and marketing of their own infrastructure.

Diverse models of OA book publishers, from university or library-based publishers to commercial publisher OA teams, surfaced many common functional needs of OAeBU data for publishers as shown in the graphic below. However, their structures resulted in unique needs tied to administrative and sales reporting, as is reflected in their individual use cases.

UNIVERSITY PRESS OA EBOOK USAGE (OAEBU) DATA USE CASES

University presses and library publishers leverage OAeBU data to support marketing, sales, and editorial strategy. They share OAeBU data to support their editors in attracting prospective OA authors and collaborating with current authors. In addition, they use OAeBU data to describe OA activity for fundraising and institutional reporting. OAeBU data may also surface trends and niches among discovery platforms, signal potential markets for print distribution or translated editions, and illuminate the impacts of OA investments. Staff roles that can benefit from OAeBU data include press directors and their editorial, sales, marketing, and grant writing teams.

Challenges to benefiting from OAeBU data stem from the need to manage, curate, and normalize inconsistent usage data provided by publishing platforms and services. Such data wrangling is time-intensive, requiring expertise in data analytics, bibliometrics, and book publishing metadata. These resource requirements apply as well to the provisioning of COUNTER-compliant reports to authors and other stakeholders, and may be beyond what's available to smaller presses. Balancing data curation and analytics to inform internal press operations against report and visualization development to meet demand is a resourcing choice smaller presses in particular must confront.

Press Director

Sales and Marketing

Editorial and Acquisition

Research Admin.

Use Case 1.

Inform marketing strategy

Personas

"I'd like to know what a reader might want from a product to then support and drive further customer interaction."

a. Understand eBook audiences and end uses

Why | How

- i. by geographic distribution
 1. to identify where there is niche content interest
 2. to understand how books are used in specific areas of the world
 3. to view what usage is like in places where OA eBooks are the only accessible option
- ii. by niche usage communities
 1. within universities
 - a. to report disciplinary access and use
 - i. by faculty
 1. in teaching, e.g. Accessing one or all chapters, or cited in a syllabus on opensyllabus.org
 2. in scholarship / research
 3. for personal interest
 4. to understand tenured vs. non-tenured usage differences
 - ii. by graduate-level students
 1. in class
 2. for scholarship
 - iii. by undergraduate students in class
 - iv. by librarians

1. in reference, advisory, and support capacity to faculty and students
2. as book purchasers
- b. to report use to university administration
- c. to report use among alumni and the broader campus community
2. within primary/grade schools (K-12)
 - a. by students
 - b. by educators
3. within industry
 - e.g. measure of access via company URLs
4. within news media and by journalists
5. within the government
 - a. impacts and references for policy-making
 - b. at multiple levels, e.g. national, state or province, city or locality
6. within other institutions
 - a. by understanding usage at institutions with an interest or specialty in particular subjects
 - b. by viewing which institutions are accessing what content
 - c. by understanding intra-institutional vs. non-institutional access
7. within the 'public' such as
 - a. local public in the university press' region
 - b. *"To show local impacts on the state and community where the press is based."*
 - c. advocates or enthusiasts for a defined subject, e.g. *"Such as gamers or environmental campaigners."*

b. Ensure fair comparisons of institutional usage

- i. by normalizing institutional data by
 1. faculty count
 2. full-time enrollment
 3. international classification systems, e.g. [World Bank country classifications by income level](#)
 4. National classification systems, e.g. [Carnegie classifications](#) - intra-USA comparison
- ii. by normalizing geographic data by
 1. per capita / population, e.g. [World Bank population estimates and projections](#)

c. Understand usage patterns and trends

- i. to investigate the demand for print copies of OA books
- ii. to understand format access patterns and frequency for OA eBook content to support reading behavior
 1. e.g. *"Do readers appear to prefer HTML or PDF?"*
 2. e.g. *"Do readers prefer versions with or without comments by other readers, by reviewers, etc.?"*

"Practices for normalizing and presenting data are still in development, but are required to ensure fair comparisons across institutions."

"Less inference is better"

3. e.g. "Do seasons or academic calendars impact usage?"
4. e.g. "Do readers prefer to read books like this cover to cover, or do they dip in to look for citation/passage?"
5. e.g. "Do readers tend to access one chapter, all chapters, >1 chapter, etc.?"

d. Understand AI and non-human usage

- i. for text or data mining
- ii. for reposting
- iii. for portal inclusion or use
- iv. for pirate site inclusion or use
- v. for abstracting
- vi. for indexing
- vii. other active uses

e. Understand OA as a discoverability tool

- i. that generates additional activity
 1. print transactions
 2. premium e-transactions
- ii. by understanding how OA books are presented on the sites librarians use to acquire books such as GOBI, ProQuest, OverDrive, BorrowBox
- iii. by understanding how OA books are presented on sites that readers use to discover scholarly content such as Google Scholar, Google.com, Academia.edu, ResearchGate
- iv. to understand what a reader might want from a product to then support or drive further customer interaction, e.g. "analog to index"

Use Case 2.

Inform sales strategy and understand OA impact

Personas

a. Suggest titles that should become OA

- i. by using comps similar to decisions based on past sales data
e.g. "Similar to how sales trends inform future potential."
- ii. by identifying geographic niches for future OA publication
e.g. "Where there is a lack of retail distribution chain but there was past demand or use of previous editions."

b. Understand the OA impact (+/-) on sales revenue

- i. by testing theories of OA impact on sales
- ii. by surfacing OA usage in Global North vs. Global South

c. Understand the amount of OA funding required to meet anticipated sales figures

d. Surface local edition or translation opportunities based on geographic use

e. Inform marketing and sales resource allocation by incorporating usage data alongside print or eBook sales data

Use Case 3.

Provide basis for exploring assumptions about OA impact

Personas

- a. Study how OA impacts gated content access
e.g. "Is paid content out in the world in the same way?"
- b. Study how OA impacts access to knowledge

Use Case 4.

Editor relations

Personas

- a. Support development of tool-kits for editors so they can be sophisticated in their use of data
- b. Provide reports to help track impact-based editor acquisitions and goal performance.
e.g. "Show the progress made on acquiring books with x amount of impact."

Use Case 5.

Analyze or benchmark OA books

Personas

- a. Examine geographic impact or use of OA books compared to similar non-OA books
 - i. by geographic range of OA readers vs. non-OA readers
 - ii. for geographic regions that OA reaches but non-OA does not
 - iii. using the percentage of total use in different regions
- b. Compile qualitative or alt-metrics for OA compared to non-OA
 - i. to provide soft measures of disciplinary impact
 1. with related prizes or awards
 2. with related reviews
 3. with related media attention
 4. with related references in tenure or promotion files
 5. with related references in disciplinary blogs or listservs
 6. with related references in public policy or grey literature
 7. with related statements from readers or users on why they're using the book, what they'd going to do with what they've learned, etc.
- c. Compile quantitative metrics for OA compared to non-OA
 - i. for readership, e.g. "Count or quantity of readers"
 - ii. for scholarly citations
 1. as quantity of citations, i.e. count
 2. by frequency of citation

"Picking the right benchmarks is going to be very important.

Clarity around standard benchmarks will be needed given many different ways to look at quantitative data."

"Examples of complementary data sources that relate to usage data to illustrate impact include Crossref Event Data and Altmetrics."

- iii. for downloads
- iv. for in-browser views, e.g. *"Internet Archive tracks"*

d. Understand online reader engagement and references

- i. on social media, e.g. Twitter
- ii. on discussion forums, e.g. Reddit
- iii. in crowd-sourced reference resources, e.g. wikipedia
- iv. on websites or blogs

e. Provide comparative metrics (i.e. apples to apples)

- i. to illustrate how a book performs compares to books in similar disciplinary area
 - 1. e.g. *"As defined by BISAC subject code."*
 - 2. e.g. *"As defined by internal subject taxonomy."*

Use Case 6.

Inform editorial strategy

Personas

a. Inform printed book version based on OA usage

- i. by providing data to influence decision to make a print version
- ii. by understanding the format and audience for a print version
e.g. *"Is this an academic or crossover trade book?"*

b. Understand course potential

c. Inform consideration of which lists, series, and subject areas that could be made OA

d. Understand usage to identify prospective authors for future projects

- i. at the chapter level, especially for certain types of monographs, e.g. anthologies, readers, edited volumes
- ii. for a given author
- iii. in a given discipline(s)
- iv. for particular components or resources in titles with multimedia components

e.g. *"How are supplemental multimedia components being used separately from the book like a song recording in an open textbook?"*

e. Identify thematic areas for acquisitions based on usage data

"Things that are valuable to small number of scholars could be overlooked or negatively impacted if editors focus on the greatest number."

f. Identify potential authors for similar books by surfacing institutions where there is a strength in the subject area

Use Case 7.

Understand impacts of OA funding

Personas

"Qualitative data is especially important to illustrate impact alongside usage metrics."

- a. **Provide funders with usage information**
 - i. to show compliance with federal or national OA dissemination mandates
 - ii. to illustrate a funder's return on investment for OA initiatives through their grantees' impact or usage
 1. across all grants
 2. for a specific grant
 - iii. to show advancement or impacts on a funder or grant program's particular objective, such as advancing K-12 or contributing to an informed citizenry/public
 - iv. to illustrate other 'broader impacts'
 - v. to calculate or understand the impacts of up-front OA investment downstream
 1. e.g. for OA investments in Open Educational Resources
 - a. by passing savings on to students
 - b. by improving equitable access to educational resources and removing barriers to low-income populations
- b. **Surface where OA publishing funding is more available**
 - i. to inform publishing of lists
 - ii. to point authors interested in OA to specific places for OA funding
- c. **Understand whether books with greater OA funding potential tend to be more viable compared to non-OA funded projects?**

"This may inform or steer list direction over time."
- d. **Understand the editorial impact on authors of the CC licenses required by different funders**
- e. **Show the changes in usage or impact for a title when it goes OA, i.e. "Before and after comparison."**
- f. **Show the impacts of OA policies and investments on**
 - i. scholarly publishing practices by understanding the degree to which public subsidies mitigate publisher risk and costs related to making books OA
 - ii. equity and social justice
 1. by understanding the potential negative or positive impacts of OA publishing requirements on non-Western European or North American researchers
 2. by understanding whether OA funding models push OA in opposition to equity/justice objectives
"Can you surface negative network externalities?"
 - iii. the [UN Sustainable Development Goals](#)
 - iv. access to information
 1. e.g. *"Is valuable research being ignored or overlooked by those who can only afford 'free'?"*
 2. e.g. *"Does usage of OA resources vs. paid-for-access in every instance reflect the value, validity, and significance of the research?"*

Use Case 8.

Author relations

Personas

a. Provide prospective authors with information

- i. on the advantages and disadvantages of OA options in their discipline
- ii. to help them understand OA impacts, value, and ROI
- iii. to surface sources of OA funding alongside other sources of income, e.g. *"Putting OA sources alongside sales, treating each book project with holistic sources of income."*
- iv. to show the impact of citations on usage, e.g. *"This is how much usage of book x comes from citations within other online works."*

b. Support authors participating in OA initiatives

- i. by providing impact information for their individual books
 1. on trends for how the books are used around the globe, e.g. *"Who is using the book, where, and how?"*
 2. on usage by the subjects of their books, such as use by the specific communities or populations studied
 3. on usage in under-served communities
 4. on crossover usage across and between disciplines
 5. on engagement by professionals and advocates outside the academy
 - a. within government or public policy-makers
 - b. by industry researchers
 - c. within not-for-profit organizations
 6. on author defined "impact" metrics, such as those specific to
 - a. the author's discipline
 - b. the book's subject community
 - c. relevant policy or public affairs

Use Case 9.

Research or grant development and administration

Personas

a. Support proposal development

- i. for digital publishing grants
- ii. for host university institutional support or matching requests for OA initiative related grants
- iii. to provide requested data such as
 1. percentage of eBooks used compared to respective hard copies
 2. eBook subject matters (including BISAC codes)
 3. who is using the eBooks
 4. how are the eBooks being used
 5. how OA affects sales (+/-), e.g. *"They're trying to figure out how much it costs to publish OA and what's scalable, sustainable, subvention amount."*

"Go beyond the numbers to tell a compelling case that OA makes a difference."

Use Case 10.

University administration reporting and relations

Personas

b. Inform impact stories for advancement or donors

- i. by creating reports for types of donors such as
 1. intra-university donors or sponsors
 2. external organizational donors, e.g. corporate foundations
 3. individual donors, both new and repeat

c. Support and inform partnership development for new initiatives

- i. with other local entities and partners
- ii. with other publishing platforms and services

a. Support career advancement, promotion, or tenure cases

b. Report on the impacts of institutional OA funding

- i. by demonstrating the global reach of the university press imprint and OA activities
- ii. to show distribution beyond where the university press normally disseminates
- iii. to demonstrate connections to university priorities based on usage
 1. e.g. "Advancing diversity, equity, and inclusion"
 2. e.g. "Influencing public policy-makers"

c. Demonstrate the value provided through university financial investment in the press

Reviewer Comments re: COUNTER usage data:

- "You would need a document which defines all relevant keywords/terms used for collecting/reporting data."
- "Going purely by platform ('platform' as defined by COUNTER), just under half of our platforms do not provide COUNTER-compliant usage reports. These vendors are generally legal publishers, and smaller publishers who may/may not know to contact organisations such as HighWire Press or EBSCO to host and report on usage. E.g. for our (Australian) university - 53 platforms/78 reports not available COUNTER-compliant, for various reasons."
- "Non-COUNTER reporting makes the aggregation of usage data labour-intensive, open to institutional interpretation as to what should be measured, with greater risk of data handling error."
- "Note that COUNTER5 vendors are required to provide both COUNTER platform reports and SUSHI harvested usage reporting. COUNTER4 must only provide platform reports."
- "For COUNTER5 reports which need to be downloaded from vendor platforms, vendors don't provide the option to pre-filter reports at the vendor platform, though COUNTER is currently looking at opportunities to improve reporting."
- "COUNTER must be involved in these discussions, as COUNTER5 can resolve much of the issues surrounding inconsistent usage data across platforms. I've asked COUNTER to also investigate potential for OER usage reporting."
- "COUNTER4 identifies HTML and PDF. COUNTER5 reports do not."
- "Possible opportunity to collaborate with COUNTER and [CAUL](#) around COUNTER and SUSHI usage data, and Australian Bureau of Statistics (ABS) who have experience collecting and aggregating data in secure online environments (depending on what data is required)."